

Two new Clavatulinae species (Caenogastropoda: Turridae) from Ghana

Dos nuevas especies de Clavatulinae (Caenogastropoda: Turridae) de Ghana

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ABSTRACT

One *Clavatula* species and one *Pusionella* species are described as new from the infralittoral of Ghana, respectively *C. petzyae* sp. nov. and *P. ghanaensis* sp. nov.

C. petzyae is compared to *C. rubrifasciata* (Reeve, 1845) and to *C. martensi* Maltzan, 1883, both similar species living in the same area. *P. ghanaensis* is compared to *P. nifat* (Bruguière, 1792), which has a large distribution off West Africa. *C. petzyae* and *P. ghanaensis* seem to be endemic from the infralittoral of western Ghana.

RESUMEN

Se describen una nueva especie de *Clavatula* y una de *Pusionella* del infralitoral de Ghana, respectivamente *C. petzyae* sp. nov. y *P. ghanaensis* sp. nov.

Se compara *C. petzyae* con *C. rubrifasciata* (Reeve, 1845) y *C. martensi* Maltzan, 1883, ambas esp.ies de aspecto similar que viven en el mismo area. Se compara *P. ghanaensis* con *P. nifat* (Bruguière, 1792), que tiene una amplia distribución a lo largo de la costa oeste africana. *C. petzyae* y *P. ghanaensis* parecen endemismos del infralitoral de la costa occidental de Ghana.

KEY WORDS: Clavatulinae, *Clavatula*, *Pusionella*, endemism, Ghana, West Africa.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Clavatulinae, *Clavatula*, *Pusionella*, endemismos, Ghana, África occidental.

INTRODUCTION

The West African Clavatulinae Gray, 1858 have not been subject to methodical revisions since the works of STREBEL (1912 and 1914), respectively devoted to the genera *Perrona* Schumacher, 1817 and *Tomella* Swainson, 1840 (renamed as *Tomellana* Wenz, 1943) and to the genus *Pusionella* Gray, 1847. As far as the genus *Clavatula* Lamarck, 1801 is concerned, KILBURN (1985) dealt only with the South African, mainly Indo-Pacific,

species, whereas BOYER AND HERNÁNDEZ (2004) focused only on the North West African *Clavatula mystica* Reeve, 1843) and ARDOVINI (2004) only on his new species *Clavatula cossignanii* from low tide level of central Senegal.

The other main works dealing with West African Clavatulinae are those of MALTZAN (1883), KNUDSEN (1952 and 1956), NICKLÈS (1950), and BERNARD (1984).

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It must be noted that KNUDSEN (1952 and 1956) lumped in the genus *Clavatula* all the species currently attributed to different genera of the Clavatulinae. POWELL (1966) restored the division of Clavatulinae into six recent genera and two fossil genera, the recent genera *Clavatula*, *Perrona*, *Tomellana* and *Pusionella* being recognized as being present off West Africa.

The present paper is devoted to the record and description of a new *Clavatula* and of a new *Pusionella* from the infralittoral of Ghana.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The two new species are studied from material belonging originally to the collection of the second author, who sampled extensively the marine mollusc fauna of Ghana for the last 25 years, snorkeling, diving, dredging and purchasing

shells and sediments from trawlers operating off the Ghanaian coast.

Comparison with similar species was based on specimens belonging to the collections of both authors, on the original descriptions and figures, and on further data from the literature.

Due to the lack of information about the chromatism of the animals, their operculum and their radula, the study of the species considered was restricted to shell morphology and decoration.

Abbreviations :

MNHN: Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris

FBC: F. Boyer collection

JHC: J. Hernández collection

PRC: P. Ryall collection

ad.: adult

juv.: juvenile

spm.: specimen

subad.: subadult

RESULTS

Subfamily CLAVATULINAE Gray, 1853

Genus *Clavatula* Lamarck, 1801

Type-species, by monotypy: *Clavatula coronata* Lamarck, 1801 (= *Pleurotoma muricata* Lamarck, 1822).

Clavatula petzyae sp. nov. (Figs. 1-6)

Type material: Holotype MNHN (Fig. 1): 16.5 x 6.3 mm; paratype 1 FBC (Figs. 2-3): 15.6 x 6.4 mm; paratypes 2 to 14 PRC: ad. and juv. spm. (larger spm.: 19.1 mm). All from the type locality.

Other material examined: FBC: 2 juv spm, Abokwa Islands, Western Ghana, 6-7 m, rocks on sand (Fig. 6). PRC: 7 ad. and juv. spm., Abokwa Islands, Western Ghana, 6-7 m, rocks on sand. - 6 ad. spm., Mudrachmi Bay, Western Ghana, 20 m, under rocks. - 6 ad. and juv. spm., Takoradi harbour, Western Ghana, 10 m. JHC: 2 ad. spm., Takoradi, Western Ghana, 10 m (Figs. 4-5).

Type locality: Off Adjua, Western Ghana, 1-2 m, in sand with rocks.

Etymology: From Petzy Ryall, wife of the second author, for her understanding and kindness about malacological duties.

Description: Holotype, adult shell (Fig. 1). Length 16.5 mm. Protoconch of 1.35 whorls, rather large (width 0.6 mm), bulbous, shaped as a Phrygian cap, smooth, shiny, of a light amberhue. Teleoconch of 8 whorls, narrow and slender, with spire profile weakly concave. Sculpture of the spire whorls consisting of a carinate sub-

sutural fold bearing on its keel weak knobs stretched along the spiral direction, with a deep and wide spiral depression below the carinate cord; base of the spire whorls showing short and thick nodulose axial ribs linked by weakly incised thick spiral cords. Last whorl ventricose, bearing 20 long and thick nodu-

lose axial ribs on its wider part, the ribs showing a stepped outline at their uppermost part and a rounded outline towards their base, six spiral cords in the interspace between ribs, joining low nodules on the ridge of the rib, a stronger nodulose spiral cord a short distance below, and a series of about 15 irregular, thinner and flat spiral cords over the base. Aperture short, about 35% of shell length, profile of outer lip arched, siphonal canal short and sinuous, siphonal sinus faintly marked, anal sinus rather deep, columellar border smooth, oblique and weakly sinuous.

Ground colour dirty white, top of the spire brownish, the coarsest sculpture bright white, lower part of the whorl light reddish brown.

Animal, operculum and radula unknown.

Distribution: Only known from western Ghana, 1-2 m to 20 m. No specimen or shell of *C. petzyae* sp. nov. is recorded from off Ivory Coast nor from the coasts between eastern Ghana and the Niger Delta (PRC and literature). Despite the fact that these areas have not been as well sampled as the infralittoral of western Ghana, it seems from information available that *C. petzyae* is endemic from this area.

Remarks: *C. petzyae* shares similar features with a poorly delimited species group including *C. bimarginata* (Lamarck, 1822), *C. rubrifasciata* (Reeve, 1845), *C. martensi* (Maltzan, 1883) and *C. filograna* (Odhner, 1923)

Clavatula bimarginata is easily distinguished from *C. petzyae* by its large size, high and rounded subsutural rim bearing weakly defined axial ribs and well-

defined squamose spiral lamellae, rather carinate periphery with rather rounded nodules and long aperture; it seems to be restricted to the Senegal region. The similar species *C. filograna*, apparently restricted to the Angolan coasts, is distinguished from *C. bimarginata* mainly by its more slender outline, its narrow subsutural rim limited to a granulate cord, and the series of narrow spiral cords covering the whole shell.

The spire of *C. rubrifasciata* resembles that of *C. petzyae*, but its spire profile is straight versus slightly concave in *C. petzyae*. The shell of *C. rubrifasciata* is larger than that of *C. petzyae*, and its protoconch is smaller (about 0.25 mm in width), acute and dull. The last whorl is more carinate in *C. rubrifasciata*, with strong, spaced and oblique short axial ribs at its wider part, with smaller, shorter and more numerous axial ribs lying along the lower keel of the whorl. The coarsest sculptures of *C. rubrifasciata* are light tan to red and the spiral interspaces light brown to blackish. *C. rubrifasciata* ranges from Senegal to Ghana (PRC), Gabon (BERNARD, 1984) and Angola (ROLÁN AND RYALL, 1999).

The elusive *C. martensi* ranges from western Ghana, where it was found in sympatry with *C. petzyae* (PRC: Abokwa Islands), to the Niger Delta (2 stations in KNUDSEN, 1952), and as far as Angola (PRC). *C. martensi* differs from *C. petzyae* principally by its slightly larger size, its smaller, acute protoconch (about 0.25 mm in width), its slightly more carinate outline at the wider diameter of the last whorl, its stronger and less numerous axial ribs, its stronger spiral cords at the lower half part of the last whorl, and its shorter siphonal canal.

Genus *Pusionella* Gray, 1847

Type-species, by original designation: *Murex pusio* Born, 1778 (= *Buccinum nifat* Bruguière, 1792).

Pusionella ghanaensis sp. nov. (Figs. 7-9)

Type material: Holotype MNHN (Fig. 7): 25.2 x 8.9 mm; paratypes 1 to 5 PRC: ad. and juv. spm. (larger spm.: 28.8 mm). All from the type locality.

Other material examined: FBC: 1 subad. spm., Adjua, western Ghana, beached from canoes (Figs. 8-9). PRC: 5 ad and subad. spm., Adjua, western Ghana, beached from canoes. - 3 ad. spm., off

Axim, western Ghana, 30-35 m, dredged in sandy mud. – 3 ad. spm, off river Ankobra, near Axim, 18-20 m, dredged.

Type locality: Off Sekondi, western Ghana, 20-30 m.

Etymology: From the type locality of the species.

Description: Holotype, adult shell (Fig. 7). Length 25.2 mm. Protoconch of 1.75 whorl, tiny (0.3 mm in width), protruding, shaped as a Phrygian cap, smooth, light mauve. Teleoconch of 9.75 whorls, smooth and shiny, apex acute, spire narrow and slender, weakly stepped, outline of the sides weakly convex, number of spiral furrows from 3 on the upper whorls to 7 on the lower whorl of the spire, the fourth and the fifth furrows below the suture being deeper and wider, the same pattern of spiral sculpture on the last whorl with a total of 23 spiral furrows, including 4 wide and deep furrows at the left of the aperture. Aperture narrow, length about 42% of total length, outer lip profile receding, siphonal canal short, sinuous and faintly twisting, siphonal notch well-marked, no anal notch, columellar border smooth, oblique and weakly sinuous.

Ground colour white, top of the spire mauve, one row of large axial light honey brown marks on the spire whorls, two rows on the last whorl separated by a white spiral gap at mid-whorl, a white spiral band at the top of each whorl, base of the shell white.

Animal, operculum and radula unknown.

Distribution: Only known from western Ghana, 18-20 m to 30-35 m. For

the same reasons than in the case of the previous species, *P. ghanaensis* sp. nov. can be considered as endemic from western Ghana.

Remarks: In many respects, *P. ghanaensis* resembles *P. nifat* (Bruguère, 1792), which is widely distributed from central Senegal to Angola, and which is rather common off western Ghana, where it was found in the vicinity of *P. ghanaensis*. *P. nifat* shows a very constant shell morphology and decoration along its whole range of distribution (FBC and PRC).

P. ghanaensis differs from *P. nifat* in having a smaller size, a more slender and less inflated outline with less stepped whorls, a mauve apex instead of a honey-brown one, numerous well-marked furrows instead of few faint ones, an attenuated narrow keel pointing at the base instead of a thickened keel with a stepped callus encompassing the base, one spiral row of long squarish light honey-brown marks on the spire whorls and two rows on the last whorl, instead of fragmented smaller dark red brown marks making a checked pattern in *P. nifat* (STREBEL, 1914). The spiral sculpture of *P. ghanaensis* matches more closely the pattern found in the group of *P. candida* (Philippi, 1848), but it differs in all other respects (STREBEL, 1914; KNUDSEN, 1952).

(Right page) Figures 1-6. *Clavatula petzyae* sp. nov. 1: holotype, off Adjua, western Ghana, 16.5 mm, MNHN. 2: paratype, same locality, 15.6 mm, FBC. 3: protoconch of the same specimen, widest diameter: 0.5 mm. 4: off Takoradi, western Ghana, 17.9 mm, JHC. 5: same locality, 18 mm, JHC. 6: off Abokwa Islands, western Ghana, 12.9 mm, FBC. Figures 7-9. *Pusionella ghanaensis* sp. nov. 7: holotype, off Sekondi, western Ghana, 25.2 mm, MNHN. 8: off Adjua, western Ghana, 22.9 mm, FBC. 9: protoconch of the same specimen, widest diameter: 0.4 mm.

(Página derecha) Figuras 1-6. *Clavatula petzyae* sp. nov. 1: holotipo, frente a Adjua, Ghana occidental, 16,5 mm, MNHN. 2: paratipo, misma localidad, 15,6 mm, FBC. 3: protoconcha del mismo ejemplar, diámetro máximo: 0,5 mm. 4: frente a Takoradi, Ghana occidental, 17,9 mm, JHC. 5: misma localidad, 18 mm, JHC. 6: frente a Islas Abokwa, Ghana occidental, 12,9 mm, FBC. Figuras 7-9. *Pusionella ghanaensis* sp. nov. 7: holotipo, frente a Sekondi, Ghana occidental, 25,2 mm, MNHN. 8: frente a Adjua, Ghana occidental, 22,9 mm, FBC. 9: protoconcha del mismo ejemplar, diámetro máximo: 0.4 mm.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ARDOVINI, R., 2004. *Clavatula cossignanii* sp. n. (Gastropoda, Turridae) dal Senegal, West Africa. *Malacologia Mostra mondiale* (Ancona), 43: 5-6.
- BERNARD, P. A., 1984. *Shells of Gabon*. Privately published pp. 1-140.
- BOYER, F. and HERNÁNDEZ, J. M., 2004. Variability and distribution of *Clavatula mystica* (Reeve, 1843). *Iberus*, 22 (1): 77-84.
- KILBURN, R. N., 1985. Turridae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) of Southern Africa and Mozambique. Part 2. Subfamily Clavatulinae. *Annals of the Natal Museum*, 26 (2): 417-470.
- KNUDSEN, J., 1952. Marine Prosobranchs of Tropical West Africa collected by the "Atlantide" Expedition 1945-46. Part I. *Videnskabelige Meddelelser fra Dansk naturhistorisk Forening i Kjobenhavn*, 114: 129-185, pls. 1-3.
- KNUDSEN, J., 1956. Marine Prosobranchs of Tropical West Africa (Stenoglossa). *Atlantide Report n°4*: 7-110, pls. 1-4.
- MALTZAN, H. F. VON, 1883. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der senegambischen Pleurotomiden. *Jahrbücher der Deutschen Malakozoologischen Gesellschaft*, 10: 115-135, pl. 3.
- NICKLÈS, M., 1950. *Mollusques Testacés Marins de la Côte Occidentale d'Afrique*. P. Lechevalier, Ed., Paris: 1-269.
- POWELL, A. W. B., 1966. The Molluscan Families Speightiidae and Turridae. *Bulletin of the Auckland Institute and Museum*, 5: 1-184, pls. 1-23.
- ROLÁN, E. AND RYALL, P., 1999. Checklist of the Angolan marine molluscs. *Reseñas Malacológicas*, 10: 1-132.
- STREBEL, H., 1912. Bemerkungen zu den *Clavatula*-Gruppen *Perrona* und *Tomella*. *Jahrbuch der Hamburgischen Wissenschaftlichen Anstalten*, 29 (2): 1-24, pl. 1.
- STREBEL, H., 1914. Mollusca I, Gen. *Pusionella*. *Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Meeresfauna Westafrikas*, 1 (2): 87-125, pl. 3.